

Report on

Auxetic Materials

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Abstract

This report examines auxetic materials which are designed to have a negative Poisson's ratio. This means they expand sideways when stretched. This unusual behaviour provides unique mechanical advantages, such as better resistance to indentation, improved toughness against fractures, and beneficial synclastic curvature, which aids in uniform bending. The document outlines the structural mechanisms involved, including re-entrant and semi-rigid shapes, and briefly explains their current applications like aerospace and defence. The report focuses on a case study on how auxetic structures can be used in Non-Pneumatic Tyres (NPTs) for city utility vehicles. The study performed Finite Element Analysis (FEA) on Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU) models, comparing three designs. The Re-entrant Hexagonal structure (Type B) showed the best results, with the lowest Von Mises stress. This indicates it manages force and distributes stress well, providing a smoother ride. However, the report highlights major challenges to commercialization. These include the compromise of basic mechanical stiffness under heavy loads and dependence on expensive, difficult-to-scale additive manufacturing methods. Future research should focus on improving material composites and scaling up production to realize the full potential of auxetic materials.

1. Introduction

Auxetic material has been around for decades, and significant amount of study has been done around the topic. Auxetic material is not a material with new chemical composition but just materials with different structural design than its parent material. This structural engineering achieves a negative Poisson's ratio which means that when a tensile force is applied longitudinally, the material will expand laterally. This report will explore these structural designs and how they affect material properties. The report briefly touches its applications like aerospace, defence, medical and looks deeply into a case study about use of auxetic materials in non- pneumatic tyres used in city utility vehicles. Using the technique of Finite Element Analysis (FEA) the case study will evaluate three different structural patterns among which one will be non-auxetic and two will be auxetic structures and find the most suitable for the application. The report investigates difficulties in commercially manufacturing the auxetic structure and its scalability for industrial purposes. The documents will also discuss the potential future work that can be done in the field of material science for these auxetic structures.

2. Background

The concept of auxetic Materials was first looked around in 1987 by Lakes when he started looking into foam.[1] Auxetic materials, structures, fabrics (or also “Auxetics”, a term that commonly groups all of them) are materials that exhibit an unexpected behaviour when they are subjected to mechanical stresses and strains. When they’re stretched in the longitudinal direction, they become thicker in one or several of the perpendicular width-wise directions or when they are subjected to uniaxial compression, they display a “thinning” in one or several of the transverse directions.[2] Auxetic materials are not new compositions developed but just a change in the structural arrangement of the material to get a auxetic property. This is achieved by getting a negative Poisson's ratio. Poisson's Ratio is the ratio between amount of lateral compression to amount of longitudinal elongation. Having a positive Poisson's ration gives it a greater Bulk Modulus (K) compared to its shear modulus (G). This implies material is easier to shear than it is to compress like rubber which has a Poisson's ratio of 0.5. While materials with negative Poisson's ration have lower K compared to G. Which signifies material is highly resistive to mechanical shear but is easier to compress.[3]

Figure 1: (A) Auxetic structure (B) Non-auxetic structure.[2]

Auxetic materials have non affine deformation which implies local strain is non uniform. The internal localized non uniform movement is precisely what generates the necessary lateral expansion when you pull longitudinally.[3] This behaviour can be obtained by various structural changes.[4]

2.1 Cellular Solid

Shapes like hexagonal honeycomb can be changed to re-entrant structure to achieve negative Poisson's ratio.

Figure 2: Re-entrant Honeycomb structure.[4]

2.2 Semi-rigid structures

Shapes like rectangle, square or triangles formed in the materials can be attached to each other in such a way that negative Poisson's ratio is obtained.

Figure 3: Semirigid Auxetic Structures.[11]

2.3 Microstructure in Polymers

When polymers form these long chains, their structure has nodules and tendons which when connected in special manner can result in negative Poisson's ratio.

Figure 4: Auxetic Polymer Structure.[4]

The change in structural arrangement results in the change of material properties. Auxetic Materials have a synclastic curvature which allows them to uniformly bend can take a dome like shape in case of force applied.[5] Changing to negative Poisson's ratio also gives the material higher indentation resistance as materials move in as the indentation force is applied.[7] It also increased strength against fracture.[8] It is observed that copper foams with auxetic structures have

about 80% to 160% increase in their J-Integral.[9] In addition, Auxetic materials also exhibit variable permeability as material contracts and expand laterally when stress is applied longitudinally.[10]

Figure 5: (a) Anticlastic (saddle-shape) curvature of a positive Poisson's ratio material and (b) synclastic (dome-shape) curvature of a negative Poisson's ratio (auxetic) material undergoing out-of-plane bending.[4]

Figure 6 : Indentation behaviour in non-auxetic (a) and auxetic (b) materials.[7]

Figure 7: Variable Permeability in Auxetic Materials.[7]

These change in properties causes vast amount of application in Aerospace and defence. Using Sandwich Panels aided by the synclastic curvature helps easier forming of the panels into desired shape. Using radomes helps keep the out atmosphere out and lets the radiation in for defence ratio stations. Uses in medical bandaging are also observers in some of the cases. Auxetic material helps precise use of antimicrobial agent for wounds. Auxetic materials can also be used in mechanical fastening as they are easy to slide in but difficult to loosen out due to negative Poisson's ratio. Uses in sensors like hydrophones have also been recorded as it increases the sensitivity of the piezoelectric sensor due to its material properties.[11]

Figure 8: Sandwich panels for Aerospace.[6]

Figure 9: Radome for Défense.[22]

3. Case Study

From Decades industries have been using Natural Rubber tyre in our most of the applications, especially in daily city utility tyres. These tyres are either made up of natural rubber, synthetic polymers with special liner inside to hold the air. Although they have long lifespans, good traction, and shock absorption they also have disadvantages. They are difficult to manufacture and recycle, easily prone to burst out or need regular maintained for air pressure. Here where the revolutionary concept of Non-Pneumatic Tyres (NPT's) come into action. They have single material and no need for air to inflate, which helps to overcome the above disadvantages.[12]

A tyre should be able to bear static and dynamic load, absorb shock, provide traction, and facilitate the steering controls. Pneumatic tyres are excellent at this. However, NPT's (Non-Pneumatic Tyres) face problems for force management on uneven surface, have rigidity (rider has bumpy ride).[13] This is where Auxetic property can be introduced to minimize the disadvantages.[14] Auxetics have higher indentation resistance, synclastic curvature and a negative Poisson's ratio which give higher G (Shear modulus) but a lower K (bulk Modulus).

The material considered in the case study is Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU). It has durability like plastic but flexibility like a rubber.[13]

Properties	TPU
Density	1180 kg/m ³
Modulus of Elasticity	129 MPa
Tensile Ultimate Strength,	55.2MPa
Tensile Strength, Yield	53.8MPa
Poisson's Ratio	0.389

Table 1: Material Properties of TPU.[13]

TPU can be easily manufactured using FFF Additive Manufacturing technology. The technology is fast, low cost, and easily accessible.[15] The case study[14] used a normal desktop printer due to two factors:

- a) highly efficient rapid prototyping
- b) easily scalable and inheritable

The case study compares the non-auxetic and auxetic structure of NPT's and identifies a better option for a city utilitarian purpose. Three designs for the NPT's have been considered. First is normal hexagon non auxetic structure (Type A). Second is a Re-entrant Hexagonal Structure (Type B). Third is the Double Arrowhead Auxetic Structure (Type C).

Figure 10: (A) Type A - Hexagon Honeycomb (B) Type B - Re-entrant Hexagonal Structure (C) Type C - Double Arrow Headed Structure.[14]

For FEA analysis of the tyres a force of 3000N, 3500N and 4000N is taken into consideration.[14] This is 408 kg of static load which is the normal case for a SUV which are the cars used for daily city used. The study is performed on the basic of Von Mises Stress. This is based on the theory of Failures where for ductile materials most of the research is done using the distortion Energy theory. This theory accounts for distortion (shape change) rather than volumetric change.[16]

Figure 11: Max. deformation comparative graph.[14]

Figure 12: Maximum von-mises stress comparative graph.[14]

The results obtained from the analysis are satisfactory. As inferred from the above data it can be observed that the double arrowhead type auxetic structure has lowest deflection among the three

types. This means at higher weight of the car the tyre will deflect less. The Von mises Stress in Re-entrant type auxetic is less which means that Type B has very less stress concentration than Type A and Type C. Thus, stress concentration points are well distributed in Type B. Type B has four times less stress at high force than Type A and about 30% less than Type C. For a city used vehicle type B is best as it handles stress distribution efficiently but at the same time it has an adequate amount of deflection so as the rider has a smooth ride.[14]

Though the Case study considers a non-auxetic structure and has given a process to manufacture the tyre, yet it is commercially difficult to produce. Also, the case study only focuses on the static loading and has overlooked a lot of key parameters like dynamic loading, tyre wear and tear, thermal parameters, and environmental conditions. Also, the case study used only single type of auxetic structural design for a tyre. Use of multiple structural designs in a single tyre may aid in reducing various defects and a better force handling which is missed in a single design strategy. This opens a lot of doors for future study and research opportunities.[14]

4. Discussion

Auxetic materials have a lot of advantages over their convers non-auxetic structure, but they are not widely used in industry. The reason being multiple of limitation around the auxetics is yet to be addressed properly. Tests have been conducted for a Polyurethane (PU) foam of Poisson's ratio = 0.4 and its auxetic form of Poisson's ratio = -0.16.[17] Under normal stress the auxetic did perform significantly better but under higher stress conditions it suffered more damage than the conventional foam. The reason being the microstructure of auxetic having those re-entrant hinges or rotating units. These became the concentrated stress points under higher load condition. So, the impact benefits of Auxetic heavily depended on the amount of impact which is not a universal solution.

The change in structural design for the auxetic has a major flaw of porosity which directly leads to change in original mechanical properties. The trade-off is between getting a negative Poisson's ratio but losing fundamental mechanical stiffness. This loss of initial stiffness is major drawback for applications like aerospace, defence, or medical prosthetic.[18] Though auxetic helps perfectly in getting those weird shapes due to its synclastic curvature property but that must compensate for the mechanical stiffness. Additionally, the material must bind with the structural change for getting that negative Poisson's ratio. It should be able to manage that buckling effect during production, just additive manufacturing the structure does not guarantee its auxetic behaviour.[19]

Moreover, manufacturing auxetics is a challenge too with only reliable way being additive manufacturing using FDM, SLS, or SLA. Industrial or usable sizes of auxetic are costly, time consuming and difficult to achieve using Additive Manufacturing. The size is not the only problem but managing those small, intricate structures throughout the large volume is not much achievable but additive manufacturing technology. Most of the auxetic are still only evaluated using the finite element analysis method rather than physical techniques due to their difficult manufacturability.[18] Manufacturing is not the only downside, achieving those specific properties at desired location is still difficult to design. Designs are based on well-established geometry like re-entrant honey come, chiral or semirigid structures. These designs have a very less strain range in which they show this negative Poisson's ratio.[20]

Auxetic have these incredible theoretical benefits of synclastic curvature, energy absorption, and better stress distribution. But these have a significant trade-off for loss of stiffness, costly manufacturability, and difficult to scale up. This gives it an exceptionally good opportunity for further research. Study around using multiple material auxetics using smart material engineering is much needed. Use of nano particles and their application techniques should be looked after.[21] Also an advancement in manufacturing techniques needs to be achieved for easy manufacturability of such structurally engineered parts.

5. Conclusion

Material with a negative Poisson's ratio is what led to the development of auxetic materials. Initial work of R. Lakes for foams what interested other researchers to investigate these materials. Materials that show indentation resistance, variable permeability, energy absorption, and synclastic curvature with just a change in its structural arrangement was quite intriguing. But the trade-off in stiffness and manufacturing difficulties is what makes auxetic behaviour still hard to implement in day-to-day use. Auxetic materials have a high potential in material science, but its scalable manufacturing and use of advanced material science is still a matter of investigation.

6. Use of AI

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